

Conference Abstract

Workshop: Engaging people in conservation of crucian carp through a citizen science approach

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Abstract

The citizen science project “Save the Crucian carp” (zachrankarase.cz/en/) in Czechia represents a successful example of public engagement in freshwater fish conservation. Initially launched as a passive platform for collecting species presence tips from the general public, it gradually gained momentum. Remarkably, many participants went beyond reporting, becoming actively involved in breeding crucian carp in privately owned ponds. Some even voluntarily paid for genetic testing to verify the purity and lineage of the fish, supporting conservation of the two distinct phylogenetic lineages present in the country. This success story serves as a valuable model that could be replicated in other countries. A key step would be translating and adapting the Czech-language website and outreach materials for international use. In this workshop, our goal is to familiarize you with the potential challenges involved in reaching target audiences, filtering citizen-contributed data, and effectively communicating the project’s objectives. We will also explore strategies for engaging participants meaningfully, such as offering incentives or recognition to ensure sustained and impactful public involvement. Citizen science is gaining momentum in the conservation of freshwater fish species, serving as an effective bridge between professional scientists and target groups within society. Media plays a crucial role in fostering this connection. Developing a user-friendly mobile application supported by an informative website can significantly enhance this engagement. Such platforms facilitate the proper dissemination of information, raise awareness, and simultaneously enable the collection of valuable data from the public.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.